

Correlation Analysis of Socio-personal Characteristics with Entrepreneurial Behaviour

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The research focused on analysing the Entrepreneurial behaviour and socio-economic analysis of mushroom growers in Haryana. The present study also analyzes the correlation between socio-personal characteristics with entrepreneurial behaviour. The present study was carried out in the two districts of Haryana, specifically Kurukshetra and Karnal. Three blocks from each district, a total of six blocks were selected purposively. This research focuses on understanding the relationship between socio-personal variables and entrepreneurial attributes among 60 mushroom growers. The study highlights that parental occupation, economic motivation, and level of social participation significantly influence the growers category. Achievement motivation exhibited a positive association with education, training, social engagement, and scientific orientation, whereas age had a negative correlation. Risk preference exhibited a positive relation with age but was negatively correlated with education and social participation. Decision-making ability was strengthened by training, social participation, and economic motivation, while age had a negative effect. Moreover, the use of online platforms was closely linked to the level of mushroom cultivation. The findings emphasize that education, social participation and motivation are crucial in shaping the entrepreneurial behaviour, strengthening decision-making abilities, and adoption of new technologies.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial behavior, education, social participation, decision-making, risk preference

Entrepreneurship is regarded as an essential pillar of national development, as it promotes efficient allocation and utilization of resources. It integrates risk-taking and innovation practices by adopting and refining production technologies to minimize expenses and improve both product quality and quantity. Furthermore, entrepreneurship also drives market diversification and enables efficient coordination and management of production operations at various levels, resulting in sustained economic growth and development (Ramappa et al., 2013). Entrepreneurial behavior encompasses the attitudes, traits, and behaviors exhibited by individuals engaged in entrepreneurial endeavors (Jose, 2020). The study and analysis of entrepreneurial behaviour has received substantial attention due to its close association with human capital and multiple outcomes associated with it (Baron and Kenny 1986, Cohen et al. 2003). It includes a variety of key characteristics such as risk-taking propensity, achievement motivation, and self-

confidence, all of which are essential for fostering entrepreneurial success. The present study was conducted in the two districts of Haryana, namely Kurukshetra and Karnal, to examine the correlation analysis of socio-personal characteristics with entrepreneurial behavior.

Method

Participants

A comprehensive list of mushroom growers was prepared with the help of the horticulture department, HDOs, ADOs, scientists from KVKs and well-known mushroom growers were contacted to gather information about the mushroom-producing entrepreneurs. In total, 60 respondents were selected as respondents for the present study by the snowball sampling method. The data collection methods include: a questionnaire was used to collect data, where a set of questions was asked to respondents to gather the required information. Interviews allow researcher to ask direct behavioral questions about their risk, achievement motivation, and decision-making ability in their mushroom enterprise. Observations were carried out by visiting their site, watching their activities and collecting data, facts and information.

Selection of Study Area

The study was conducted in the Kurukshetra and Karnal districts of Haryana. These two districts are among the highest mushroom-producing districts in Haryana. Three blocks from each of the two districts were selected purposively because they had the highest mushroom production in these two districts.

Measure and Procedure

The selection of variables in this analysis resulted from a

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comprehensive review of the literature and discussions with subject matter experts. As per the objectives of the study, the variables like scientific orientation, latest information seeking behaviour, risk preference, achievement motivation, use of an online platform and decision-making ability were quantified with the help of available measurement procedures. The collected data was analysed using SPSS software. The statistical techniques, including frequency, percentage, standard deviation, total weighted score, total mean score, and rank order, were employed to develop meaningful inferences from the data. The responses collected from the respondents were appropriately coded and analysed using SPSS software. Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to test the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The formula employed is as follows:

$$r = \frac{n(\Sigma xy) - (\Sigma x)(\Sigma y)}{\sqrt{[n\Sigma x^2 - (\Sigma x)^2][n\Sigma y^2 - (\Sigma y)^2]}}$$

Where,

n - Number of observations being correlated

Σxy - Sum of product of X and Y

x and y - The variables being correlated

Σx - Summation of overall cell entries of the first variable

Σy - Summation of overall cell entries of the second variable

Σx^2 - Sum of all squared values of each cell of first variable

Σy^2 - Sum of all squared values of each cell of second variable

Results and Discussion

Coefficient of Correlation between Independent Variable and Types of Growers

The correlation analysis presented in Table 1 revealed that parental occupation, economic motivation, and social participation are significantly associated with the type of growers, whereas variables such as age, gender, education, marital status, landholding, experience, and training, area under mushroom cultivation, production, extension contact, scientific orientation, and information-seeking behavior are not. Parental occupation is significant in that individuals whose parents are engaged in agriculture or related occupations may grow up with greater exposure to farming practices, networks, and norms, making it easier to adopt a particular grower type (commercial, specialized, etc.). Economic motivation being positive and significant suggests that growers who are strongly driven by financial returns are more likely to invest effort, adopt innovations, or scale up, aligning with the grower types characterized by higher input, risk or output orientation. Social participation probably plays an enabling role with growers who are active in social groups, cooperatives, or farming networks are more likely to exchange knowledge, access opportunities, and get support, which helps them to become more specialized or commercial growers. Also, many demographic or structural variables did not show significance. Gender and Education may be non-significant because women and men may be equally involved or because gender roles do not strongly differentiate grower types in your locale and the kinds of knowledge required are learned on the job or via informal networks rather than formal schooling. Marital status, landholding, and experience might not matter if mushroom cultivation (or your crop) involves a relatively small area or less dependence on large land size or long experience compared to other crops, reducing the influence of these

variables. Training received, extension contact, scientific orientation, and information-seeking behavior may be evenly distributed among growers or may not translate into different grower types if other enabling factors (capital, market access, inputs) are constrained; in other words, knowing is necessary but not sufficient. Similarly, area under cultivation and actual production may not differ sufficiently between grower types in your sample to show correlation.

Table 1

Correlation between Independent Variable and Types of Growers

Sr. No.	Variables	Type of Grower	
		'r' values	Sig.
1.	Age	0.088 ^{NS}	0.505
2.	Gender	0.282 ^{NS}	0.029
3.	Education	0.159 ^{NS}	0.226
4.	Marital status	0.149 ^{NS}	0.256
5.	Parental occupation	0.258*	0.047
6.	Landholding	0.103 ^{NS}	0.434
7.	Experience	0.146 ^{NS}	0.266
8.	Training received	0.159 ^{NS}	0.226
9.	Area under mushroom cultivation and production	0.092 ^{NS}	0.485
10.	Social Participation	0.370**	0.004
11.	Extension Contact	0.062 ^{NS}	0.639
12.	Economic Motivation	0.326*	0.011
13.	Scientific Orientation	0.073 ^{NS}	0.579
14.	Latest information-seeking behaviour	0.106 ^{NS}	0.420

Note: ** - Significant at the 0.01 level, * - Significant at the 0.05 level, NS - Non-Significant

Coefficient of Correlation between Independent Variable and Achievement Motivation of Mushroom Growers

The correlation analysis presented in Table 2 indicated that age is negatively and significantly correlated with achievement motivation among mushroom growers, whereas variables such as education, experience, and training received, area under cultivation, production, social participation, extension contact, economic motivation, scientific orientation, and recent information-seeking behavior are positively and significantly correlated. Landholding also shows a positive and significant relationship, but at a lower significance level. In contrast, gender, marital status, and parental occupation do not show significant effects. A plausible explanation is that younger growers tend to have higher drive, energy, and openness to change, which boosts their achievement motivation more than older growers, who may prefer stability or are constrained by physical, financial, or health limitations. Meanwhile, education improves one's ability to understand best practices, innovations, and opportunities; experience builds self-confidence and skill; and training provides technical know-how and exposure to new ideas. Together, these raise the likelihood that growers set ambitious goals. Greater area under cultivation and higher production can reinforce achievement motivation because these are tangible measures of success. Participation in social groups or networks, extended contact, and seeking new information provide sources of feedback,

encouragement, and social recognition, which all bolster motivation. Economic motivation and scientific orientation reflect internal aspirations and value placed on progress and efficiency, also contributing positively. On the other hand, gender, marital status, and parental occupation may not show significance either because in your sample these do not strongly differentiate opportunity or resources, or because motivational aptitudes across these categories are more uniform. The results of achievement motivation align with (Bhattacharjee et al., 2025).

Table 2

Correlation between Independent Variable and Achievement Motivation

Sr. No.	Variables	Achievement Motivation	
		'r' values	Sig.
1.	Age	-0.389**	0.002
2.	Gender	0.302 ^{NS}	0.019
3.	Education	0.464**	0.000
4.	Marital status	0.088 ^{NS}	0.503
5.	Parental occupation	0.025 ^{NS}	0.852
6.	Landholding	0.302*	0.019
7.	Experience	0.372**	0.003
8.	Training received	0.554**	0.000
9.	Area under mushroom cultivation and production	0.372**	0.003
10.	Social Participation	0.509**	0.000
11.	Extension Contact	0.380**	0.003
12.	Economic Motivation	0.339**	0.008
13.	Scientific Orientation	0.535**	0.000
14.	Latest information-seeking behaviour	0.363**	0.004

Note. **- Significant at the 0.01 level, *- Significant at the 0.05 level, NS- Non-Significant

Coefficient of Correlation between Independent Variable and Risk Preference

The correlation analysis in Table 3 results indicate that age is positively and significantly correlated with mushroom growers' risk preference, whereas education, experience, training received, area under cultivation, production, social participation, extension contact, economic motivation, scientific orientation, and latest information-seeking behavior all bear negative and significant correlations. Landholding also shows a negative and significant relationship at the 0.05 level. Gender, marital status, and parental occupation do not show significant associations with risk preference. It indicates that older growers may be more willing to accept risk in mushroom cultivation, perhaps because they have accumulated experiential knowledge, asset buffers, or a greater tolerance for uncertainty over time. In contrast, younger or better-educated growers, with more awareness of potential losses and more access to alternative livelihood options, may exhibit more risk aversion. The strong negative association with education suggests that education might foster more cautious or informed decision-making, reducing tendencies toward risky strategies. Likewise, enhanced experience, training, extension contact, and higher information seeking behaviour may reduce risk-taking by improving growers' ability to anticipate uncertainties, resulting them more secure and stable decisions. A larger cultivation area and high

production level may increase the risk, encouraging growers to be more cautious and avoid uncertain decisions. Social participation and economic motivation may also shape growers' decision-making in accordance with community norms or peer pressure that favour more cautious strategies. The negative correlation with scientific orientation indicates that those who are inclined towards scientific and data-driven methods tend to avoid highly uncertain or speculative decisions. The slight negative correlation with landholding indicates that growers possessing more land may prefer to minimize risk and be less interested in risky practices. The non-significance of gender, marital status, and parental occupation suggests that in your sample, these factors do not strongly influence growers' predisposition toward risk.

Patil and Veetil (2024) found in eastern India that elder farmers tend to be more risk-averse and that education positively influences choices of less risk-averse options, suggesting that education can moderate risk behavior. In research focusing on cotton farmers in Tamil Nadu, higher education, membership in organizations, and extension contacts were associated with lower risk-taking, further supporting the negative role of these variables in cultivating risk preference. Also, a recent study on farmers in eastern India revealed the heterogeneous nature of risk attitudes and showed that socioeconomic factors like education and assets significantly influence risk orientation and adoption of agricultural practices.

Table 3

Correlation between Independent Variable and Risk Preference

Sr. No.	Variables	Risk Preference	
		'r' values	Sig.
1.	Age	0.354**	0.005
2.	Gender	0.339 ^{NS}	0.008
3.	Education	-0.486**	0.000
4.	Marital status	0.034 ^{NS}	0.797
5.	Parental occupation	0.041 ^{NS}	0.753
6.	Landholding	-0.264*	0.041
7.	Experience	-0.349**	0.006
8.	Training received	-0.488**	0.000
9.	Area under mushroom cultivation and production	-0.364**	0.004
10.	Social Participation	-0.606**	0.000
11.	Extension Contact	-0.341**	0.008
12.	Economic Motivation	-0.422**	0.001
13.	Scientific Orientation	-0.472**	0.000
14.	Latest information-seeking behaviour	-0.462**	0.000

Note. **- Significant at the 0.01 level, *- Significant at the 0.05 level, NS- Non-Significant

Coefficient of Correlation between the Independent Variable and Decision-making Ability

The correlation coefficient in Table 4 suggests interesting patterns with respect to the correlates of decision-making ability among mushroom growers. A negative and significant association was observed between age and decision-making ability, indicating that the younger growers comparatively have better decision-making skills. Whereas, training received, area under cultivation, mushroom

production, social participation, economic motivation, scientific orientation, and information-seeking behavior are all positively and significantly correlated with decision-making ability. Further, landholding, experience received, and extension contact are also positively correlated, but at a lower level of significance. Variables such as gender, marital status, and parental occupation do not show a significant association. It indicates that younger growers are more adaptable to get new information, more innovative, and cognitively adaptable, resulting in improved decision-making capabilities. Older growers stick to the conventional method and are less inclined to evaluate alternative options, and show a negative correlation. Education increases the thinking capacity, ability to analyze alternatives, and take better decisions. Training gives us hands-on knowledge, exposure to decision methods, and feedback, therefore enhancing our decision-making capabilities. A larger cultivation area and higher production level imply that growers have more at risk, which drives them to make decisions more carefully. Social participation encourages exposure to various viewpoints, collective learning and discussion, which contributes to improved decision-making skills. Economic motivation encourages growers to make decisions more strategically to get maximum returns. Scientific orientation motivates growers to apply data-driven decision rules, helps them avoid random or intuitive choices. Ultimately, information seeking demonstrates proactive efforts and alertness in collecting essential data before making choices, which directly contributes to better-informed decisions. The weaker but positive relationships of landholding, experience, and extension contact suggest that having more resources (land), being more familiar with farming tasks (experience), and having access to formal agricultural services (extension) provide supportive contexts for better decision making. On the other hand, gender, marital status, and parental background may not directly influence a grower's internal decision competence, or their effects may be mediated through other factors.

These findings align with Indian agricultural research that highlights the importance of education, training, social participation, and extension in enhancing farmers' decision-making capacities. For example, "Farmers' Decision Making Pattern on Agricultural Innovations: A Process Analysis" (Gowda et al., 2022) examines Indian farmers' decision processes and emphasizes how knowledge and information sources support more informed decision making.

Table 4

Correlation between Independent Variable and Risk Preference

Sr. No.	Variables	Decision-making ability	
		'r' values	Sig.
1.	Age	-0.373**	0.003
2.	Gender	0.315NS	0.014
3.	Education	0.408**	0.001
4.	Marital status	0.031NS	0.815
5.	Parental occupation	0.040NS	0.759
6.	Landholding	0.285*	0.027
7.	Experience	0.303*	0.018
8.	Training received	0.526**	0.000
9.	Area under mushroom cultivation and production	0.467**	0.000
10.	Social Participation	0.573**	0.000
11.	Extension Contact	0.294*	0.022
12.	Economic Motivation	0.451**	0.000

13.	Scientific Orientation	0.452**	0.000
14.	Latest information-seeking behaviour	0.480**	0.000

Note. **- Significant at the 0.01 level, *- Significant at the 0.05 level, NS- Non-Significant

Coefficient of Correlation between Independent Variable and Use of an Online Platform

The correlation coefficient in Table shows that area under mushroom cultivation and production is the only variable that is positively and significantly correlated with use of an online platform. All other variables including age, gender, education, marital status, parental occupation, landholding, experience, training received, social participation, extension contact, economic motivation, scientific orientation, and information-seeking behavior, were non-significant (with correlations ranging from $r = -0.154$ to $r = 0.225$). This suggests that growers who operate larger areas or higher production volumes are more likely to adopt online platforms, perhaps because greater scale creates stronger incentives to access broader market linkages, digital tools, or e-commerce opportunities to optimize sales, reduce marketing costs, or gain price advantages. In contrast, demographic and socio-psychological factors may not directly influence online adoption in your sample; digital uptake may depend more on economic necessity or scale than on individual traits.

Table 5

Correlation between Independent Variable and Use of an Online Platform

Sr. No.	Variables	Use of an Online Platform	
		'r' values	Sig.
1.	Age	0.117 ^{NS}	0.375
2.	Gender	0.143 ^{NS}	0.277
3.	Education	0.154 ^{NS}	0.239
4.	Marital status	0.225 ^{NS}	0.084
5.	Parental occupation	0.166 ^{NS}	0.204
6.	Landholding	0.092 ^{NS}	0.486
7.	Experience	0.099 ^{NS}	0.453
8.	Training received	0.140 ^{NS}	0.287
9.	Area under mushroom cultivation and production	0.345**	0.007
10.	Social Participation	0.083 ^{NS}	0.527
11.	Extension Contact	0.203 ^{NS}	0.119
12.	Economic Motivation	0.010 ^{NS}	0.941
13.	Scientific Orientation	0.060 ^{NS}	0.649
14.	Latest information-seeking behaviour	0.041 ^{NS}	0.755

Note. **- Significant at the 0.01 level, *- Significant at the 0.05 level, NS- Non-Significant

Conclusion

The research establishes that socio-personal attributes such as parental occupation, economic motivation, and social participation play a major role in shaping the entrepreneurial behaviour of mushroom growers in Haryana. Achievement motivation is positively associated with education, training, and social engagement, whereas age shows a negative influence. Age and

education influence the risk-taking behaviour, while decision-making ability improves with proper training and motivation. The use of online platforms for technology adoption is associated with the scale of cultivation of mushrooms. The results emphasize the importance of targeted education, training, and social support to enhance entrepreneurial skills, decision-making, and technology use, resulting in sustainable rural development and better livelihoods.

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